

1 **Crosslinked pH-responsive Polymersome via Diels-Alder Click Chemistry: a**
2 **Reversible pH-dependent Vesicular Nanosystem**

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6 **Abstract**

7 Herein, we have developed pH-responsive shape-persistent polymersomes made of well-
8 defined amphiphilic poly(ethylene oxide)-*block*-poly(diisopropylaminoethyl methacrylate-
9 co-furfuryl methacrylate)s PEO-*b*-P(DPA-co-FMA) by exploiting Diels-Alder chemistry as a
10 robust and simple crosslinking method. Using Photo-induced Copper Mediated Reversible
11 Deactivation Radical Polymerization, we synthesized PEO-*b*-P(DPA-co-FMA) with optimal
12 block ratios that favor the formation of polymersomes in aqueous media having pH-
13 responsive P(DPA-co-FMA) membranes. Owing to the existence of furfuryl pendant
14 groups within the polymersome membranes, the crosslinking of pH-responsive P(DPA-co-
15 FMA) chains can be achieved *via* Diels-Alder chemistry. Interestingly, the resulting
16 crosslinked polymersomes swell when the pH in the solution is decreased so that it lies in
17 a biologically relevant range, as was demonstrated by cryogenic transmission electron
18 microscopy. Here, the polymersomes' ability to swell can be controlled by adjusting the
19 amount of crosslinker. A minimum threshold of crosslinking density is needed for the
20 polymersomes to swell while an excess amount of crosslinker quenched their ability to
21 swell. Furthermore, crosslinked polymersomes are capable of encapsulating hydrophilic
22 model drug, such as Rhodamine B. At pH 7.20, due to the compact and hydrophobic
23 membrane, the diffusion of the dye from the interior of the polymersomes to the media is
24 minimized, while the protonation of PDPA at an acidic pH of 4.00, enables a permeable
25 membrane, allowing the loaded cargo to leak much more quickly. The shape-persistent
26 polymersomes that we developed herein, are a promising nano-platform for use in drug
27 delivery applications.

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1 Introduction

2 pH-responsive polymers are interesting candidates for use in delivery and sensor
3 applications that are associated with changes in the local pH (for example, within the
4 tumor microenvironment). For biomedical applications, a pH transition in the range of 5.5
5 (lysosomal) to 7.4 (physiological) is desired.[1-3] Among polymers having pH-
6 responsiveness in this range, poly(diisopropylaminoethyl methacrylate) (PDPA) is one of
7 the most promising candidates. Indeed, as reported in literature, PDPA-based polymers
8 have a tunable pH transition in the range of 5.5 to 7.0, which can be used in
9 intracellular/intratumoral drug delivery systems and in sensors for tracking
10 endosomes/lysosomes.[4-6] Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that PDPA is much
11 less cytotoxic than other tertiary amine-based polymers such as poly(2-
12 (dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate) (PDMAEMA) and poly(2-(diethylamino)ethyl
13 methacrylate) (PDEAEMA).[7, 8] Amphiphilic PDPA-based block copolymers have been
14 demonstrated to be robust, versatile platforms in the construction of pH-responsive
15 nanoparticles for intracellular pH-sensing and drug delivery applications. [9-14] Depending
16 on the nature and relative volume fraction of each block, the copolymer morphology can
17 vary from spherical micelles to cylinders (or worms) to polymersomes (or vesicles) to
18 tubular polymersomes, each one of which interacts differently with living mammalian
19 cells.[15-21] Similar to a liposome configuration, a polymersome has a thick hydrophobic
20 polymer membrane which encapsulates a water interior. Such a structure enables the
21 encapsulation of either hydrophobic or hydrophilic molecules (or both) into a single
22 nanocarrier while their pH responsiveness, enables their use as advanced delivery
23 systems.[4-6, 22-28]

24 pH-responsive polymersomes dissociate to form single polymer chains when the solution's
25 pH is lower than the pH transition. In contrast, the shape-persistent vesicles obtained *via*
26 the crosslinking of a polymersome's membrane undergo swelling without complete
27 disassembling.[29, 30] Furthermore, since they have a more rigid and compact membrane,
28 crosslinked polymersomes might behave differently with regard to cellular interaction
29 compared to polymersomes that have not been crosslinked. Therefore, research should be
30 dedicated to the development of PDPA-based shape-persistent polymersomes. However,
31 most of the studies that have been reported in literature focus on the crosslinking of
32 PDPA-based nanostructures with a micellar morphology, while the ones on polymersomes
33 remain less explored.[31-33] Several groups have studied crosslinked polymersomes

1 based on other tertiary-based polymers such as PDMAEMA or PDEAEMA using silanol
2 condensation or photo-cycloaddition of dimethyl maleimide.[29, 30, 34] However, their high
3 toxicity is a major concern regarding their potential use in applications. Therefore, more
4 efforts have been made to develop nanostructures based on PDPA and having pH-
5 responsive shape-persistent features. The first example was reported by Armes' group,
6 which synthesized PDMAEMA-*b*-PDPA and produce micelles with a PDPA core and a
7 PDMAEMA shell in aqueous media.[33] To crosslink the PDMAEMA domain, they used
8 1,2-Bis(2-iodoethoxy)ethane (BIEE) as crosslinker by quaternizing dimethyl amino
9 pendants. Using a similar technique, Bütün and coworkers synthesized crosslinked "onion-
10 like" triblock copolymers made of PDPA, PDMAEMA and poly[2-(N-morpholino)ethyl
11 methacrylate] respectively.[32] In another approach, Giacomelli synthesized PEO-*b*-PDPA
12 with an junction-block made of poly(glycerol monomethacrylate) (PG2MA), which later
13 underwent a crosslinking process *via* the Michael addition reaction using divinyl sulfone as
14 a crosslinker and triethylamine as a catalyst.[31] Despite these successful examples, the
15 crosslinking methods mentioned above still have some major drawbacks. For instance,
16 quaternization might lead to an unexpected positive surface charge, and it is necessary to
17 use an excess amount of a crosslinker in each of these cases. Furthermore, for both
18 methods, to make nano-objects crosslinkable, one needs to introduce reactive groups to
19 them, and this is a relatively complicated process which involves multi-step synthesis of
20 well-defined block copolymers.

21 Over the past few decades, Diels-Alder click chemistry has been proven to be a reliable
22 and versatile technique for the preparation of functional materials.[35, 36] The most
23 commonly used Diels-Alder reaction in materials science is that between electron-deficient
24 diel furfuryl and maleimide, since cycloaddition can be induced at a relatively low
25 temperature and several monomers that contain furfuryl are commercially available.[35,
26 36] Another interesting feature is that the resulting crosslinked nanostructures become
27 thermo-responsive due to the reversible nature of Diels-Alder chemistry, and this cannot
28 be achieved using any other crosslinking technique.[35, 37-39] Indeed, furfuryl-maleimide
29 cycloaddition has been successfully exploited to crosslink several polymeric micelles, [37-
30 40] but there have not yet been any reports on the use of this technique to produce
31 polymersome systems or pH-responsive based structures.

32 In this study, we investigated the feasibility of using the Diels-Alder crosslinking technique
33 to achieve shape-persistent pH-responsive polymersomes based on biocompatible PDPA.

1 We first demonstrated the controlled polymerization of DPA using Photo-induced Copper
2 Mediated Reversible Deactivation Radical Polymerization (PI-CMRDRP) in two solvent
3 systems including DMF/2-PrOH and DMF/MeOH. This polymerization technique was later
4 extended to synthesize PEO-*b*-PDPA with different degrees of PDPA polymerization (DP)
5 in order to identify the best block length ratios for the formation of polymersomes. Furfuryl
6 methacrylate (FMA) was then incorporated into the PDPA segments to obtain PEO-*b*-
7 P(DPA-*co*-FMA), and the self-assembly process of such polymers in aqueous solution was
8 studied. Later bis-maleimide as crosslinker was *in situ* encapsulated within the membrane
9 of PEO-*b*-P(DPA-*co*-FMA) polymersomes during self-assembling to promote Diels-Alder
10 click chemistry of the polymerosome membrane. This resulted in a shape-persistent pH-
11 responsive polymersomes. Subsequently, the dependence of the structural changes as
12 well as the response of such polymersomes to pH, on the crosslinking density, was also
13 revealed. The ability of such crosslinked pH-responsive polymersomes to encapsulate
14 hydrophilic molecules, such as the drug model Rhodamine and release them in a pH-
15 mediated trigger manner was also demonstrated.

16 **Results and discussion**

17 **Synthesis of PEO-*b*-PDPA by PI-CMRDRP**

18 To synthesize well-defined PEO-*b*-PDPA, we chose to use the PI-CMRDRP
19 polymerization technique due to its versatility and reliability. In order to investigate the
20 optimal conditions for block copolymers to grow, we first demonstrated that a PDPA with a
21 controlled molar mass and low dispersity can be synthesized using PI-CMRDRP. In doing
22 so, we performed a kinetic study on two different solvent systems (including DMF/MeOH
23 and DMF/2-PrOH). A detailed description of the experimental procedure can be found in
24 the supporting information, SI (Figure S1, S2 and S3). Then, poly(ethylene oxide) which
25 had been functionalized with a bromide initiator and DPA monomers were used to prepare
26 well-defined PEO-*b*-PDPA, exploiting PI-CMRDRP, as is shown in Figure 1a.

1

2 **Figure 1. Polymerization of PEO-*b*-PDPAs using PI-CMRDRP.** (a) Schematic representation of
 3 the steps in the synthesis of PEO-*b*-PDPAs. (b) ¹H NMR spectra of PEO-*b*-PDPA. The
 4 measurements were performed using CDCl₃ as a solvent at 25 °C. (c) The SEC traces of the
 5 macro-initiator, BP 30, BP40 and BP48. The measurements were performed using THF as a
 6 solvent, and PS was used for the calibration.

7 In the first step, monomethoxy polyethylene oxide (PEO-OH) was treated with 2-
 8 bromoisobutryl bromide (2-BriBuBr), following a protocol that had previously been
 9 reported in literature.[41] The success of this functionalization step was confirmed by ¹H
 10 NMR spectroscopy (Figure S4). ¹H NMR spectrum of pristine commercial PEO-OH shows
 11 two characteristic peaks for the ethylene oxide (-O-CH₂-CH₂O-, 3.88 – 3.45 ppm) back
 12 bone and methoxy group (CH₃-O-, 3.40 ppm) at the beginning of the chain. Upon the
 13 reaction with 2-bromoisobutryl bromide, the appearance of two new peaks which are
 14 characteristic for methylene protons that are linked to the ester group [-O-CH₂-CH₂-O-
 15 C(=O)-, 4.34 ppm] and for the methyl protons closed to the bromine [(CH₃)₂>C(-C)-Br, 1.96
 16 ppm], respectively (Figure S4), indicates that the initiating sites bound successfully to the
 17 PEO chains. Interestingly, thanks to the purification step, all the peaks that corresponds to
 18 impurities in the pristine PEO-OH vanished, indicating that the PEO-Br became more pure.

1 Subsequently, a PDPA block was grown from the 2-bromoisobutyrate group of the PEO
 2 chains using similar conditions that were applied to the kinetic study in DMF/MeOH. In the
 3 first experiment, a monomer/initiator ratio of 20 was used, and the polymerization time was
 4 kept for 8 h rather than 4 h used for kinetic study. The block copolymers were purified by
 5 dialysis against acetone using a regenerative cellulose membrane bag (MWCO: 1000
 6 g.mol⁻¹), and the solvent was removed under a reduced pressure. A successful
 7 functionalization step was confirmed by ¹H NMR measurements. In the ¹H NMR spectrum
 8 (Figure 1b), all the characteristic PEO and PDPA block peaks could be clearly detected.
 9 By comparing the integrals of the peaks for ethylene oxide (b, -O-CH₂-CH₂-O-, 3.75 - 3.40
 10 ppm) and for the methylene group that was linked to nitrogen (f, -CH₂-N<, 3.12 - 2.91 ppm)
 11 in the DPA side chains, it was possible to determine the degree of polymerization (DP) and
 12 thus the precise molar masses of the block copolymers. The DP was determined by ¹H
 13 NMR spectroscopy using the equation below:

$$DP = \frac{2 \times 44 \times \int_{3.40}^{3.75} d\delta}{\int_{2.91}^{3.12} d\delta}$$

14
 15 Where $\int_{3.40}^{3.75} d\delta$ and $\int_{2.91}^{3.12} d\delta$ are the integration of the chemical shift from 3.75 – 3.40 ppm
 16 (ethylene oxide protons in a PEO block) and 3.12 – 2.91 (methylene proton adjacent to
 17 carbonyl group in the PDPA block, proton f), respectively. In order to achieve a set of
 18 PEO-*b*-PDPA polymer molecules with different block lengths, the feeding ratios of
 19 monomer/initiator were changed from 20 to 40, as is shown in Table 1.

20 **Table 1.** List of parameters used for the synthesis of PEO-*b*-PDPA by PI-CMRDRP at different
 21 DPA unit lengths.

Entry ^a	[PEO-Br]	[DPA]	Conversion (%)	M _n NMR theory (g.mol ⁻¹)	M _n NMR real (g.mol ⁻¹)	M _n SEC (g.mol ⁻¹)	Đ
PEO-Br	1	-	-	2000	2000	3000	1.05
BP30	1	20	90	5800	7500	9000	1.11
BP40	1	30	92	7900	9600	10000	1.16
BP48	1	40	91	9700	11800	11400	1.13

1 ^aThe polymerization was carried out in a mixture of DMF:MeOH (3:1), the volume of the solvent is
2 4 mL. 1.0 g PEO-Br (M_n : 2000 g.mol⁻¹) macro-initiators were used in each entry. The molar ratio of
3 [MPEO-Br]:[CuBr₂]:[PMDETA] was 1:0.04:0.13.

4 As is shown in Table 1, three diblock copolymers of PEO₄₄-*b*-PDPA_x called BP30, BP40
5 and BP48 (i.e. BP_x, where *x* is the degree of polymerization) were successfully
6 synthesized. The resulting block copolymer structures were also confirmed by ¹H NMR
7 measurements. SEC analysis (Fig 1c) revealed that the dispersity (\bar{D}) of all the samples
8 was very low (lower than 1.16), indicating that the polymerization by PI-CMRDRP occurred
9 in a controlled manner even when a polymer-based initiator was used. Interestingly, the
10 signal of PEO-Br completely vanished, and the chromatograms revealed that the block
11 copolymers had a high degree of purity of the after purification, which is crucial for self-
12 assembly.

13 The big difference between the theoretical and the real molar masses indicates that the
14 macro-initiator deactivated during the polymerization step. Based on the extent of this
15 difference, an initiation efficiency of 60.0% was determined for BP30. The same trend was
16 recorded for BP40 and BP48, for which the initiation efficiencies were 67.5% and 75.0%,
17 respectively. Thus, it would seem that the increase in the monomer/initiator ratio in solution
18 improves the initiation steps. Since the volume of solvent was kept constant for all the
19 trials, the increase in monomer/initiator ratio caused the volume of the solution to become
20 augmented which, in turn, led to a decrease in the initiator concentration. As the
21 termination rate is proportional to the square of the radical concentration, such a dilution of
22 the initiator might result in formation of fewer initiating radicals in the early stages of the
23 polymerization, which would thus suppress the termination, leading to a quenching of the
24 initiator.[42] However, the initiation step for copper-mediated radical polymerizations is
25 rather complicated; it depends on several parameters such as the interaction between the
26 monomer molecules and the metal complex and the reaction conditions.[43-45] To
27 summarize, it was possible to control the molar masses of the resulting block copolymers
28 by varying the monomer/initiator ratios using PI-CMRDRP. The resulting block copolymers
29 that were synthesized here with a low dispersity are good segments for self-assembly
30 studies in aqueous solution.

31 **Self-assembly of PEO-*b*-PDPA in aqueous solution**

32 The self-assembly of PEO-*b*-PDPA in aqueous solution was investigated using two
33 different casting approaches: by slowly adding the polymer solution in THF as non-

1 selective solvent to water as selective solvent (Method 1); and by gradually adding water
2 to the polymer solution in THF (Method 2) (Schemes in figure 2a and 2b). Since PDPA is
3 not soluble in water at neutral pH, the switching of media from THF to a water-rich media
4 induces the self-assembly of PEO-*b*-PDPA to form nanostructures. In the first set of
5 experiments, method 1 and PEO-*b*-PDPA were used (Figure 2a). In this approach, the
6 block copolymer was dissolved in THF because it is a good solvent for both blocks. This
7 solution was then added dropwise into water. Next, the THF was removed by slow
8 evaporation (24 h), and the pH, measured after the THF had been completely removed,
9 was found to be around 7.35, which is higher than the pH transition of PDPA (pK of 6.8 -
10 7.0).

11 Interestingly, significant differences between the BP30, BP40 and BP48 were observed in
12 this step. The aqueous solution was clear upon the addition of BP30, and it remained
13 transparent after THF had been removed (Figure S5a). Therefore, small micelles formed,
14 as was confirmed by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) measurements (Figure 2a).
15 However, a blueish solution was obtained as soon as BP48 was added to water, and it
16 became more translucent after the block copolymer solution had been added and the THF
17 had been removed (Figure S5b). This phenomenon indicates that large particles formed,
18 which could be micelles, polymersomes or worm-like structures. The same observation
19 was made in the case of BP40 (data is not shown).

1

2 **Figure 2. Preparation and characterization of BP30 and BP48 nanostructures.** Sketch of the
 3 synthesis steps and DLS traces (number-weighted) of BP30 (black), BP40 (red) and BP48 (blue)
 4 nanostructures in water (pH 7.4) using Method 1 (a) and Method 2 (b). Cryo-TEM images of the
 5 BP48 nanostructures using (c) Method 1. The Inset shows a high magnification of micelles. In
 6 method 1, out of 160 particles counted, 90 % of the population is micelles (< 50 nm) (d) and (e)
 7 refer to the BP48 nanostructures that were made using Method 2. Out of 62 particles counted, 65%
 8 of them is small polymersomes (50÷100 nm) and 25% of them is large polymersomes (100 ÷ 150).
 9 White and black arrowheads point to the micelles and polymersomes respectively. The black dots
 10 represent 10 nm Au NCs as reference markers.

11 As expected, the hydrodynamic diameter (number-weighted) that was recorded for BP30
 12 had the lowest value (which was 16 nm) whereas the values found for BP40 and BP48
 13 were 27 and 29 nm, respectively (Figure 2a, inset). Notably, increasing the PDPA by 10
 14 units from 30 to 40 caused a significant change in diameter (10 nm), while increasing the
 15 PDPA length even further from 40 to 48 did not increase it much more (it only increased by

2 nm). The same trend was observed when the diameters were calculated by volume and intensity (Figure S6a and S6c). Such observations can be explained by the fact that the dominant structure of the PEO-*b*-PDPA self-assembly changes from smaller to bigger nanostructures. For example, the micelles transformed to polymersomes when the length of the PDPA was increased from 30 to 40 units. However, the polydispersity (PDI) of all the measurements was very high (above 0.24), indicating that the solution contained a variety of nanostructures with a broad range of shapes and sizes. Cryogenic-transmission electron microscopy (Cryo-TEM) was further used to monitor the morphologies of BP30 and BP48 in water. As expected, small micelles with an average size of 16.9 ± 6.1 nm (Figure S7) were observed in the BP30 sample, which was in a good agreement with the results of the DLS measurement. Interestingly, a various morphologies were observed in the case of BP48 (Figure 2c). Here, not only small micelles, but also polymersomes could be detected, which resulted in the nanoparticles having an average size of 36.0 ± 15.4 nm (Figure S8a). The existence of polymersomes with sizes ranging from 30 to 110 nm explains the very high dispersity that was obtained from DLS measurements. In order to further investigate the self-assembly process, we also studied the gradual addition of water to the polymer solution in THF (Method 2). As it has already been demonstrated in literature, the gradual addition of water generally leads to a slow switching of the media, which allows block copolymers to reach their equilibrium .[17, 46] In this case, block copolymer was first dissolved in THF. To this solution, water was added dropwise at a rate of $2 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. To ensure a high degree of homogeneity, the solution was agitated by means of magnetic stirring. The pH value for all the samples upon THF removal was found to be 7.4. Also in this case similar observations as compared to the ones using Method 1 were made. The solution of BP30 kept the transparency during all the steps of the experiment while BP40 and BP48 were permanently translucent during the water addition and upon removal of THF (Figure S5b).

Table 2. A comparison of the hydrodynamic size of PEO-*b*-PDPA diblock copolymers that self-assembled in water using different techniques

Sample	Diameter (number-weight, nm)		Diameter (volume-weighted, nm)		PDI	
	Method 1	Method 2	Method 1	Method 2	Method 1	Method 2
BP30	16	34	21	42	0.62	0.09
BP40	27	93	35	123	0.28	0.09

BP48	29	115	63	150	0.24	0.07
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1 All the measurements were recorded using a PBS (pH 7.4) as media.

2 DLS revealed that the hydrodynamic diameter (number-weighted) of BP30 was 34 nm,
3 which is two times higher than it was when it was prepared using the previous techniques
4 (Figure 2b, inset). This increase in the size was also observed when BP40 and BP48 were
5 used. Interestingly, the hydrodynamic sizes of BP40 and BP48 (number-weighted) were
6 much higher than the ones that were obtained using Method 1 (see Table 2), which could
7 be associated with the formation of vesicular structures. The same trend was observed for
8 the volume-weighted diameter (Figure S6b). Remarkably, the polydispersity of all the
9 measurements was very low, as the PDI values were all below 0.1. It would appear that
10 this casting technique offers better control over self-assembly, therefore nanoparticles with
11 a higher homogeneity were obtained. The morphology of the nanostructure that was
12 obtained from BP48 using Method 2 had vesicular structure, as was confirmed by TEM
13 (Figure 2d and 2e). Even though there is still a certain amount of micelles present,
14 statistically, the majority of the nanostructures in the solution are polymersomes (see the
15 histogram of the sizes, Figure S8b). The average size of these nanoscale vesicles is
16 around 85.9 ± 45.2 nm, which is close to the ones that were obtained from DLS.

17 **pH-responsiveness of PEO-*b*-PDPA nanostructures**

18 Since the formation of such nano-micelles and polymersomes originates from the
19 hydrophobic nature of the PDPA blocks at pH 7.4, the protonation of the tertiary amine
20 core (upon lowering the pH so that it lies in the acidic range) will induce a dissociation of
21 the nanostructures. To evaluate the pH transition of the PEO-*b*-PDPA, as well as that of its
22 self-assembled structures, pH dependent DLS measurements were performed using the
23 samples that were obtained using Method 2.

1
2 **Figure 3.** Hydrodynamic diameter (intensity-weighted) of the BP30 (green), BP40 (red) and BP48
3 (black) diblock copolymers in water as function of pH. The polymer concentration for the
4 measurement was *ca.* 0.5 mg.mL⁻¹. The samples were dissolved in a buffer and kept for 3 minutes
5 so that they could reach their equilibrium prior to performing the measurements.

6 The BP30, BP40 and BP48 nanostructures were all stable when the pH > 7.11, as the
7 changes in the intensity-weighted hydrodynamic diameter were negligible (Figure 3). For
8 the vesicular structures (BP40 and BP48), the nanoparticle size seemed to be more
9 sensitive to the pH of the solution than for the micellar one (BP30 has the shortest
10 hydrophobic block). Interestingly, once the pH of the solution was further reduced to 7.01,
11 the hydrodynamic diameters of all the samples significantly dropped (to ~ 9.0 nm), which
12 could be assigned to the dissociation of the nanostructures to free single polymer chains in
13 solution. Based on this explanation, it can be assumed that the a pH transition of all the
14 block copolymers lies between 7.11 and 7.01, which is in good agreement with the values
15 that have been reported in literature.[4, 24-28] These results suggest that the pH-

1 responsiveness of PEO-*b*-PDPA is independent of the length of the PDPA block and on
2 the self-assembly processes.

3 Synthesis of PEO-*b*-P(DPA-co-FMA) by PI-CMRDRP

4 We also explored the possibility of performing the crosslinking of such polymersomes
5 using Diels-Alder click chemistry. For this purpose, furfuryl methacrylate was introduced to
6 the PDPA block to yield PEO-*b*-P(DPA-co-FMA), as is illustrated in Figure 4a.

7
8

9 **Figure 4. Preparation and characterization of furfuryl modified PEO-*b*-P(DPA).** (a) Scheme of
10 the synthesis steps of PEO-*b*-P(DPA-co-FMA) using PI-CMRDRP; (b) A sketch showing the
11 reversible crosslinking that occurs when the temperature is changed (c) A sketch representing the
12 ¹H NMR spectrum of PEO₄₄-*b*-P(DPA₄₈-co-FMA₁₂) (SP2, the subscription indexes describe the
13 number of repeating units).

14 The presence of furfuryl moieties would allow a reversible crosslinking of the resulting
15 nanostructures to occur by means of Diels-Alder click chemistry using 1,1'-(Methylenedi-
16 4,1-phenylene)bismaleimide (BM) as crosslinkers (Figure 4b). To ensure that a
17 polymersome structure forms upon self-assembly in aqueous media, the total expected
18 degrees of polymerization (DPA and FMA) were fixed to be 40 (SP1) and 50 (SP2) and the
19 molar percentages of FMA were aimed at 20% to provide a sustainable crosslinking
20 probability. A successful synthesis of PEO-*b*-P(DPA-co-FMA) was confirmed by ¹H NMR
21 spectroscopy. Figure 4c shows the ¹H NMR spectrum of SP2, while the one of SP1 can be

1 found in Figure S9. In the spectra, the resonant signals at 7.40 ppm (-O-CH=), 6.45 ppm (-
 2 O-CH=CH-), 6.40 ppm (-CH=C<) and 5.0 ppm (-CH₂-) can be easily assigned to the
 3 furfuryl pendants. All the other characteristic PEO and PDPA block peaks as well as the
 4 methacrylate backbone can also be detected, as is evident from the spectrum. Based on
 5 the integration of the characteristic signals in the ¹H NMR spectra, molar masses of 12300
 6 and 14000 g.mol⁻¹ could be determined for SP1 and SP2 respectively. We also observed
 7 that the PEO-based initiator deactivated when the block copolymer started to grow, as the
 8 theoretical molar masses were found to be lower than the real ones in both cases.
 9 Interestingly, the molar masses that were obtained from ¹H NMR and SEC are very similar
 10 to each other, as is shown in table 3.

11 **Table 3.** The detailed parameters for the synthesis of PEO-*b*-P(DPA-*co*-FMA) by PI-CMRDRP

Entry ^a	[PEO-Br]	[DPA]	[FMA]	Total conversion (%)	M _n NMR theory (g.mol ⁻¹)	M _n NMR real (g.mol ⁻¹)	M _n SEC (g.mol ⁻¹)	Đ
SP1	1	32	8	90	9300	12200	12300	1.22
SP2	1	40	10	91	11500	14200	14000	1.21

12 ^aThe polymerization is carried out in a mixture of DMF:MeOH (3:1), the volume of the solvent is 4
 13 mL. 1.0 g PEO-Br (M_n: 2000 g.mol⁻¹), and macro-initiators were used in each entry. The molar ratio
 14 of [MPEO-Br]:[CuBr₂]:[PMDETA] was 1:0.04:0.13.

15 In addition, low Đ values were obtained in both cases (1.22 for SP1 and 1.21 for SP2),
 16 along with mono-modal SEC chromatograms (Figure S10), and these indicate that the
 17 copolymerization occurred in a controlled manner, regardless of the initial composition.
 18 Interestingly, the molar ratio of furfuryl methacrylate was found to be 20% in both cases,
 19 which is in a good agreement with the feeding ratios.

20 **Self-assembly of PEO-*b*-P(DPA-*co*-FMA) and polymersome crosslinking via Diels- 21 Alder Chemistry**

22 The self-assembly of PEO-*b*-P(DPA-*co*-FMA) (SP1 and SP2) in an aqueous solution was
 23 performed by adapting method 2 (which was used for PEO-*b*-PDPA), as above described.
 24 As expected, a milky solution could be obtained upon the addition of water in both cases,
 25 indicating that a polymersome structure was formed (data not shown). A d_H of 156 nm
 26 (number-weighted) was recorded when SP1 was used for the self-assembly experiment

1 (Figure S11a), while the polymersomes made of SP2 showed a hydrodynamic size of 190
 2 nm. The SP2 polymersomes are likely bigger since their hydrophobic segment is longer
 3 (number-weighted) (Figure S11b). To crosslink the polymersomes, the BM crosslinker was
 4 co-dissolved with the block copolymer in THF. During the water addition, crosslinker was
 5 *in situ* encapsulated within polymersome membrane (see the scheme in Figure 5a). After
 6 THF evaporation, the crosslinking process was initiated by heating the solution at 60 °C for
 7 16 h. The amount of block copolymer was fixed to be 10 mg (which corresponds to a final
 8 concentration of 1 mg.mL⁻¹), while the molar ratio between the BM crosslinker and furfuryl
 9 methacrylate (crosslinking density) was varied from 15 to 60%. A ratio higher than 60% led
 10 to the precipitation of naked-eye visible aggregates.

11

12 **Figure 5. Preparation and characterization of crosslinked polymersomes.** Schematic
 13 representation of the swelling of crosslinked polymersomes as a result of changes in the pH (a).
 14 The d_H (b and d) and swelling capability (c and e) of crosslinked polymersomes as a function of the
 15 crosslinking density using SP1 (b and c, respectively) and SP2 (d and e, respectively). Images of

1 average ($n=10$) cryotomographic slices of crosslinked polymersomes using SP2 (crosslink density
2 of 45%) at pH 7.4 (f) and pH 3.0 (g) (see corresponding Supplementary movies, video S1 and S2).

3 When SP1 was used, it was observed that the d_H of the polymersomes decreased as the
4 crosslinking density (CD) increased (Figure 5b). A CD of 60% led to a hydrodynamic size
5 of 110 nm, which is smaller than the one that was observed for non-crosslinked
6 polymersomes (156 nm). It is possible that the increase in the crosslinking density lead to
7 a more compact and rigid polymersome membrane. Therefore, a smaller hydrodynamic
8 size is recorded with increasing the crosslinking density. To further confirm this
9 observation, we measured the d_H at two different pH levels of 7.4 and 5.5. At pH 7.4, the
10 d_H of crosslinked polymersomes as a function of CD exhibits mostly identical values and
11 trend in comparison to their d_H measured in water (Figure 5c). The d_H measurement on
12 crosslinked polymersomes at pH 5.5 (Scheme in Figure 5a) revealed that there is a strong
13 correlation between the swelling capacity and the CD. Here, we postulated that the
14 protonation of PDPA segments significantly enhances the water solubility of the membrane
15 and promotes the swelling of such a vesicular nanostructure. It was found that there is a
16 threshold to entirely crosslink the membrane of such polymersomes. At pH 5.5, a $d_H \sim 10$
17 nm measured for non-crosslinked polymersomes indicates that they dissociated, while the
18 crosslinked polymersomes with a CD of 15% show a d_H of 24.0 nm. This proves that the
19 membrane partially crosslinked. A CD of 30 % caused the polymersomes' membrane to
20 entirely crosslink, and, therefore, polymersomes swell rather than dissociate at pH 5.5.
21 This leads to a significant increase in the d_H . The increase in the d_H at pH 5.5 for the
22 polymerosome with a CD at 60 % in comparison to the one measured at pH 7.4 was
23 almost negligible (Figure 5c and 5e). Thesa data suggest a more compact and rigid
24 membrane, which subsequently compromised the ability of the polymersomes to swell.
25 Similar observations have also been reported by Voit's group for pH-responsive
26 polymersomes crosslinked *via* a photo-induced cycloaddition of dimethyl maleimide
27 pendants.[30]

28 When a block copolymer with a longer hydrophobic segment was used (SP2), the d_H
29 (weighted by number) also decreased as the CD increased, except for when the CD. was
30 30%. Moreover, the d_H (measured by the intensity and volume) tends to increase as the
31 CD increases up to 45%, but it decreases significantly at a CD of 60%. We might
32 speculate that this phenomenon could be due to the distribution of the BM crosslinker
33 within the hydrophobic membrane in combination with the relative hydrophilic/hydrophobic
34 balance between the PEO and P(DPA-co-FMA) blocks in the self-assembling process.

1 Regardless, also in this case, the correlation between hydrodynamic size of the
2 crosslinked polymersomes and pH level follows the trend that was observed in the case of
3 SP1. Also for SP2, the CD threshold to entirely crosslink the polymersomes' membrane is
4 30%. Interestingly, we were also able to perform experiments even when the concentration
5 of polymer (SP1 and SP2) was increased by two times (so that the final polymer
6 concentration was 2 mg.mL^{-1}) without facing any problems regarding the stability of the
7 polymersomes. In this case, the d_H is higher than when a lower polymer concentration (1
8 mg.mL^{-1}) was used. Nevertheless, identical experimental trends in terms of d_H swelling
9 capability could be also obtained, as is shown in Figure S12.

10 The morphologies of the cross-linked polymersomes at a basic and acidic pH were further
11 investigated by means of Cryo-TEM. After it had been incubated at 60°C , the
12 polymersome solution that was made using SP2 and a CD of 45% (SP2-45) was
13 concentrated until a polymer solution of approximately 5 mg.mL^{-1} . The pH of this solution
14 was measured to be 7.5, and a Cryo-electron tomography characterization was then
15 performed (Figure 5f and Supplementary videos S1 and S2). To obtain the polymersomes
16 at a swelling state for the Cryo-TEM measurement, a few drops of a Hydrochloric Acid
17 solution (0.1 M) was added to this solution until the pH reached 3.0. The addition of HCl
18 dramatically increased the transparency of the solution, but it remained translucent,
19 indicating that the polymersomes swelled, rather dissociated (Figure S13). As expected,
20 the Cryo-electron tomographic images of SP2-45 at pH 7.4 revealed that the structure is
21 vesicular, which further confirms that neither the encapsulation of the BM crosslinker nor
22 the heating at 60°C (used to induce the formation of Diels-Alder adducts) altered the
23 morphology of the resulting nanostructures in this case (Figure 5f). However, the
24 tomographic images of the same sample at pH 3.0 showed a similar vesicular structure
25 with a much less dense membrane showing also a more porous structure (Figure 5g). The
26 membrane was thicker and the overall size of the polymersomes was bigger at pH 3.0
27 than they were at pH 7.4 (Figure S14). Furthermore, the 3D model that was constructed
28 using cryo electron tomography supports these observations (Video S1 and S2) and thus
29 confirming the ability of the crosslinked polymersomes to swell.

30 **pH-responsiveness and swelling reversibility of crosslinked polymersomes**

31 It has already been reported that the incorporation of other hydrophobic monomers into
32 PDPA chains may led to a shift in the pK_a of the resulting nanostructure toward an acidic
33 pH.[24-27, 34] SP2-45 with a crosslinking density of 45% was selected as a representative

1 sample to investigate the response of the crosslinked polymersomes. As is shown in
2 Figure 6a, the d_H of SP2-45 remains stable at a pH range between 7.5 and 5.8 (without
3 any noticeable changes), and it has a diameter of about 200 nm. At pH of 5.5, the d_H
4 clearly increases, which indicates that the crosslinked polymersomes swell. Here, the
5 incorporation of 20% FMA and of a crosslinking density of 45% has led to a shift in pK_a
6 from 7.05 to 5.65 (Figure 6a).

7

8 **Figure 6. Characterization of the crosslinked polymersomes' swelling.** The hydrodynamic
9 diameter (number-weighted) of the crosslinked polymersomes (black square) that were made
10 using SP2 and a CD of 45% in water as function of pH (a). d_H of crosslinked polymersomes using
11 SP1 with a crosslinking density of 30% upon reversibly switching the pH between 7.4 and 5.0 five
12 times (b).

13 We also verified the reversible swelling ability of the crosslinked polymersomes by
14 alternating the pH cycle from neutral to acidic conditions for 3 cycles in a row. For this
15 purpose, the pH of solution was repeatedly adjusted between 7.4 and 5.5 for 3 cycles
16 using HCl and a NaOH solution (0.01 M). The corresponding d_H were recorded, and we
17 were able to confirm the reversibility of the SP2-30 polymersomes, since the d_H fluctuated
18 between pH 7.4 and 5.5 (Figure 6b) for up to 3 cycles. The steady change in
19 polymersomes' hydrodynamic diameter after the first cycle, may be assigned to the
20 gradual release of the un-crosslinked block copolymers from the membrane.

21 **Encapsulation of hydrophilic molecules and release induced by pH-switching**

22 We have investigated the potential use of such crosslinked polymersomes as smart nano-
23 carriers to encapsulate a hydrophilic drug and induce a pH-mediated release. For this
24 purpose, we selected SP2-30 a presentative sample due to its high swelling capability.

1 Rhodamine B was used as a model drug due to its good water solubility and bright
2 photoluminescence. The encapsulation of Rhodamine B, and its subsequent pH-induced
3 release, was achieved following the O'Reilly's group's procedure.[22] SP2-30 and
4 Rhodamine B were first dissolved in DMF to promote the permeability of the
5 polymersomes and enable the diffusion of the dye molecules into the nanoscaled vesicles.
6 When the media was switched by adding an excess amount of water, the polymersomes'
7 membrane became compact, trapping the Rhodamine B inside the interior. Unloaded dyes
8 were removed by dialysis cycles against water. For verifying the dye release at pH 7.2 and
9 pH 4.0, in parallel, the same volume of Rhodamine B-loaded SP2-30 was dialyzed for 3 h
10 against water at neutral or acidic pH. As expected, the fluorescent signal of the dialysates
11 for the sample that was dialyzed against water at pH 7.2 was very low, indicating that a
12 compact and rigid PDPA membrane prevents the dye from diffusing out of the
13 polymersomes' interior (Figure 7). On the contrary, an eleven times higher
14 photoluminescent dye signal was obtained at pH 4 (Figure 7). At pH 4.0, PDPA chains get
15 protonated, the polymersomes' membrane becomes porous and, therefore, the dye
16 molecules can diffuse out of the polymersomes interior much more quickly. To confirm that
17 the difference in fluorescent signal is not due to the fact that Rhodamine B is more
18 fluorescent at pH 4.0, we also carried out a control experiment to compare the pH-
19 dependent fluorescent signal of Rhodamine B at pH 4 and pH 7. . Indeed, having a
20 solution at the same dye concentration, the Rhodamine B signal is actually less fluorescent
21 at pH (the signal drops by 20% in comparison to the one measured at pH 7.2 and we are
22 actually underestimating the released amount of Rhodamine B at pH 4, Figure S15).
23 These data could validate the pH-triggered release feature of the crosslinked
24 polymersomes. This system is a promising candidate for developing pH-triggered smart
25 nanomedicine.

1

2 **Figure 7. pH-induced triggered release of hydrophilic molecules from pH-responsive**
 3 **crosslinked polymersomes.** The fluorescent signal of dialysate that was collected when the SP2-
 4 30 encapsulated Rhodamine B was dialyzed for 3h against water at pH 7.2 (red curve) is 11 times
 5 lower than the one obtained when the same sample was dialyzed against water at pH 4.0 (black
 6 curve).

7

8 **Conclusions**

9 We have developed a robust and versatile synthetic route to achieve shape-persistent pH-
 10 responsive polymersomes based on poly(diisopropylaminoethyl methacrylate) (PDPA) by
 11 employing PI-CMRDRP and Diels-Alder as crosslinking chemistry. A PI-CMRDRP of DPA
 12 occurs at a rapid rate, with a good degree of control over the molar masses, and a low
 13 dispersity (which was proven by a kinetic study). This technique can also be extended to
 14 prepare well-defined amphiphilic pH-responsive PEO-*b*-PDPA and PEO-*b*-P(DPA-*co*-
 15 FMA), showing that this polymer can self-assemble in an aqueous solution to form
 16 colloiddally stable polymeric nanostructures. By tuning the molar mass ratio between pH-
 17 responsive PDPA polymer segment and hydrophilic PEO block, optimal block *co*-polymer
 18 could be identified to favor the formation of polymersomes having a spherical vesicles
 19 configuration. Moreover, we were able to demonstrate that pH-responsive polymersomes
 20 made of PEO-*b*-P(DPA-*co*-FMA) can be crosslinked by means of Diels-Alder click
 21 chemistry. In such nanosystems, the swelling and responsiveness of the polymersomes'
 22 membrane can be controlled by simply tuning the crosslinking density. It was shown that a

1 crosslinking density higher than 30% resulted in a more rigid and compact polymersome
2 membrane, restricting their ability to swell at a pH that is lower than the pH transition.
3 Instead, by using a crosslinker density of 30%, we were able to trigger at acidic pH, the
4 release of hydrophilic dyes, previously encapsulated inside the crosslinked polymersomes.
5 Given their pH-responsive characteristics, we believe that the smart nano-systems could
6 be used as pH-triggered drug delivery systems.

7 **Supporting information:** The following information can be found in the Supporting
8 Information: a list of the materials used; a description of the experimental steps and
9 polymerization kinetic study; ¹H NMR and SEC traces of polymers; and DLS, Cryo-TEM
10 and other characterizations of self-assembled nanostructures.

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1 Table of Contents

2

3

Figure 1
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Figure 2
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Figure 3
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Figure 4
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Video S1_Illustration of Crosslinked Polymersomes at pH 7

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Video S2_Illustration of Crosslinked Polymersomes at pH 3

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*Highlights

- PDPA-based polymer is synthesized by photo-induced living radical polymerization.
- PEO-*b*-PDPA self-assembles in water to form either micelles or polymersomes.
- The membranes of pH-responsive polymersomes are crosslinked by Diels-Alder Chemistry.
- Crosslinked polymersomes reversibly swell upon the switching the pH of the media.
- Crosslinked polymersomes show the pH-triggered release of pre-loaded hydrophilic dye.